

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Usar 1, a salinity- and alkalinity-tolerant rice for Uttar Pradesh

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Usar 1, a medium-maturing salinity- and alkalinity-tolerant rice variety, was released in May 1984 for cultivation in Uttar Pradesh. It was developed in Kanpur from Jaya/Getu and tested in the All India Coordinated Saline-Alkaline Resistance Varietal Trials in 1980-82 (Table 1) and in station trials from 1978 to 1983 (Table 2). Usar 1 is semitall, tillers moderately, matures in 128-135 d, and has high yield potential. Grains are short and bold with

good cooking quality. It is resistant to bacterial leaf blight and bacterial leaf streak, and moderately resistant to major

insect pests. Usar 1 is a good substitute for Jaya and traditional varieties in alkaline areas. □

Table 2. Performance of Usar 1 in state and coordinated varietal trials. UP, India.

Year and location	Yield (t/ha)		CD at 5%	Days to maturity		pH
	Usar 1	Jaya		Usar 1	Jaya	
Daleep Nagar, Kanpur						
1978	2.9	1.7	0.5	132	134	9.3
1979	3.7	2.1	0.6	133	134	9.5
1980	1.5	0.6	0.8	135	136	9.2
1981	5.3	4.6	1.1	132	135	9.1
1982	4.0	3.5	0.7	134	134	9.6
1983	4.2	3.5	0.8			
Kumarganj, Faizabad						
1978	3.0	2.0	0.4	128	132	9.1
1980	4.0	2.8	0.6	132	135	9.5
1981	4.0	3.5	0.5	134	136	9.5
1982	3.8	3.3	0.9	140	145	9.5

Table 1. Grain yield and ancillary characters of Usar 1 and Jaya at various locations, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Trial, 1982 kharif. ^a UP, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)							Days to 50% flowering	Panicles/m ²
	Alkaline locations			Saline locations					
	Raipuram	CSSRI Karnal	Kumarganj Faizabad	Pondicherry	Panvel Raigarh	Keshpur	Vytilla		
Usar 1	1.7	3.4	3.8	0.9	2.4	1.1	9.5	101	348
Jaya	1.5	2.2	3.3	1.94	2.6	0.3	6.6	106	249
CD at 5%	ns	1.3	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.4	ns		
pH	9.5	9.1-9.8	9.6	na	7.5	6.0	na		
Ec	3.5	na	1.2	na	2.5-5.2	3.5-5.0	na		

^a ns = nonsignificant, na = not available.

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HIGH TEMPERATURE

Tolerance of two rice lines for high temperature at meiosis and anthesis

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Growth chamber and field experiments have shown that rice plants are susceptible to high temperatures at reproductive stage. Studies at IRRI have shown that rice plants are most sensitive to high tempera-

ture during anthesis, and are slightly less sensitive about 10 d before flowering (booting or meiotic stage). Several varieties with tolerance for high temperature during anthesis have been identified. The most common tolerance mechanism appears to be the ability to maintain high anther dehiscence and pollen shedding at high temperatures. The relation between tolerance at anthesis and tolerance at meiotic stage has not been determined. We

compared tolerance at those growth stages.

Four rice varieties were planted in 3.8-litre pots in the IRRI phytotron on 2 dates in 2 replications. Treatments were control (29°C day/21°C night), 35°C/27°C for 5 d during flowering, and 35°C/27°C for 5 d beginning about 12 d before flowering. Each pot had 20 plants, tillers of which were trimmed to leave 1 main culm per plant. Flowering dates of each panicle were recorded.

Because it was difficult to time the heat treatment during meiotic or booting stage, only two varieties gave sufficient data over all dates of the experiment. The average percentage of filled grains for panicles flowering on different dates is shown in the figure. Data from both high temperature treatments were combined. At least three panicles were used for each average. Those flowering after the temperature treatment are on the negative side of 0 in the figure (treated before flowering) and those flowering before the treatment are on the positive side.

IET4568 was moderately tolerant in a previous study, but was relatively susceptible in this study. The two most susceptible stages were anthesis and about 10 d before anthesis, which confirms previous results. IR2006-P12-12-2-2 was highly tolerant of high temperature at anthesis in previous studies. In this study, it was tolerant at anthesis and meiotic stages.

In control treatments, IET4568 had an average fertility of 74% and IR2006 had an average of 92%, confirming earlier studies showing that heat-tolerant varieties have higher fertility even under control conditions. It is not clear if the toler-

Average filled spikelets percentage for panicles flowering on different days in relation to a high temperature treatment. The 5 d treatment of 35/27°C was given on days -2 to 2, and is shown by the shaded bar.

ance mechanism is the same for both stages. It may be that the high anther dehiscence of IR2006 allows it to overcome the high temperature damage caused during the meiotic stage, as

well as at anthesis. This line should be an excellent donor of high temperature tolerance for breeding programs for semi-arid countries where temperature is high during flowering. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Assessment of cold tolerance of Korean rice varieties by chlorophyll fluorescence analysis

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Visual assessment of cold injury based on chlorosis, browning, leaf rolling, and necrosis of rice leaves is subjective and time-consuming, especially because some of the symptoms appear only after prolonged cold or when temperatures rise. We evaluated the potential of chlorophyll fluorescence analysis for quantitative assessment of cold damage because it is

quick and can detect damage before visual symptoms appear.

When a leaf is illuminated, the chlorophyll in the membranes of the chloroplasts emits a red fluorescence of which a part, the variable chlorophyll fluorescence, is responsive to photosystem II activity. Any stress such as cold, frost, drought, or pollutants that affects photosynthetic metabolism is likely to change the fluorescence. We measured fluorescence with a plant productivity fluorimeter. The machine uses a probe that is placed on the adaxial surface of the leaf to provide the illumination and collect the fluorescent light.

In the experiment, we chilled 11 Korean rices with a range of chill sensitivity for 8 d at 10°C, 85% relative humidity, under a 12-h day cycle at 30,000 lux. The

plants were 60 d old and were grown in the glasshouse in Jul and Aug. For each variety, 5 flag leaves were randomly selected and 3 readings made at the leaf base, middle, and tip. The values are the mean of 15 readings. Fluorescence measurements were made after 5 h dark acclimation at 27°C for the controls and at 10°C for the chilled plants.

Changes in fluorescence emission occurred during the first 3 s after illuminating a dark-adapted leaf (Fig. 1). Light caused the chlorophyll fluorescence to rise immediately to 0 and this initial level is termed F_0 . Fluorescence slowly increased to a peak F_{max} , which is attained at p . For quantifying cold injury, the rate of rise of variable chlorophyll fluorescence (F_R) is the most important parameter and can be calculated by drawing a straight line to